

ing areas of north and northeast Thailand.

During 1981, 12 nonglutinous lines from RD7 mutants plus resistant varieties from India were screened in a

greenhouse at the Rice Protection Research Center, Bangkok, using gall midges from a mass rearing culture. Two RD7 mutants — RD7^{77G} CO-55-3-5-1 and RD7^{77G} CO-77-9-1-1—

were resistant to gall midge (Table 2). All Indian rice varieties except W1263 were susceptible, confirming the results of the International Gall Midge Biotype Collaborative Project. *h*

Evaluation of National Screening Nursery against rice thrips

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National Screening Nursery entries were field tested for resistance to rice thrips

Baliothrips biformis Schmutz at the RRS, Kapurthala. Thirty-five-day-old seedlings of each entry were planted 1 seedling/hill in two 5-m rows. Hills were spaced 15 × 15 cm with 20 cm between rows in each selection and 40 cm between selections. TN1 was included as the susceptible check. Entries were scored for thrips damage 20 days after transplanting (growth

stage 2) by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (1980).

Of 384 entries, 3 were scored 1; 19, 2; 107, 3; 186, 4; 59, 5; 6, 6; and 2, 7. Average score was 4. The 3 entries given a score of 1 (most resistant) were IET8200 (Hansraj/Saket 4), IET8258 (Hema/Vikram/Rajeswari/CR57-1523) and IET8283 (Tellahamsa/CR126-42-5). *h*

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Salt tolerance of mangrove swamp rice varieties

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Development of salt-tolerant rice varieties would help stabilize rice production and make expansion of cultivable land possible in mangrove swamps of West African countries where salinity is a major limiting factor. Studies to develop

improved salt-tolerant varieties adapted to mangrove conditions were started in 1979.

A method to rapidly evaluate rice variety and breeding line salt tolerance by comparing seedling root growth in salin-

Root lengths, root increments, and tolerance ratios (TR) of salt-tolerant and some moderately tolerant mangrove swamp rice varieties^a, Rokupr, Sierra Leone.

Variety	Root length (cm) in culture solution		Root increment (cm)	Root length (cm) in 80 mM NaCl solution		Root increment (cm)	TR
	7 DS	11 DS		13 DS	17 DS		
<i>Tolerant</i>							
Pa Merr 108A	2.9	7.9	5.0	8.6	11.1	2.5	0.50
Pa Foday Yoreh 260	1.3	5.5	4.2	5.9	8.0	2.1	0.50
Gassiline 193B	1.9	6.8	4.9	6.9	9.2	2.3	0.47
Pa Fant 213	1.3	6.7	5.4	7.1	9.3	2.2	0.41
Pa Rice Mill 199	1.9	8.2	6.3	8.5	11.1	2.6	0.41
Pa Bathurst 32A	1.4	4.9	3.5	4.8	6.2	1.4	0.40
Ginsa Killing 408	1.6	7.0	5.4	7.2	9.7	2.5	0.46
Majako 334	4.8	8.5	3.7	8.7	10.4	1.7	0.46
Janeh Kano 469	2.7	6.7	4.0	6.9	8.7	1.8	0.45
Banjul Ba 355	1.8	6.2	4.4	6.5	8.3	1.8	0.41
Kaopa Wolengo 443	3.0	6.5	3.5	7.0	8.4	1.4	0.40
<i>Moderately tolerant</i>							
SR 26 ^b	2.6	7.2	4.6	8.0	9.8	1.8	0.39
BD 2 ^b	2.2	6.9	4.7	7.7	9.5	1.7	0.36
Rok 8 ^b	4.6	7.9	3.3	8.5	9.5	1.0	0.30
Rok 4 ^b	5.0	8.7	3.7	9.4	10.4	1.0	0.27
Rok 5 ^b	3.4	7.9	4.5	8.2	9.4	1.2	0.27
Rok 9 ^b	4.9	8.3	3.4	8.6	9.5	0.9	0.27
Phar Com En ^b	3.2	7.4	4.2	8.2	9.2	1.0	0.24
Atahna 311A	3.8	8.0	4.2	8.2	9.6	1.4	0.33
Pa Sorro 104A	1.8	7.7	5.9	8.8	10.1	1.3	0.22
Nkumbandingo 405	3.5	10.7	7.2	10.9	12.0	1.1	0.15
<i>Checks</i>							
Pokkali (tolerant)	5.5	10.0	4.4	10.2	12.5	2.3	0.52
IR28 (sensitive)	2.0	6.5	4.5	6.4	6.6	0.2	0.04

^aDS = days after sowing. TR = $\frac{\text{root increment over 4 days in salinized culture solution}}{\text{root increment over 4 days in nonsalinized culture solution}}$. ^bRecommended variety.